

Rice and wheat yield and P removal by year as affected by P fertilization, Ludhiana, India.

Applied P (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)					P removal (kg/ha)				
	1st	2d	3d	4th	Mean	1st	2d	3d	4th	Mean
<i>Wheat</i>										
0	1.9	1.3	2.1	1.7	1.8	5.5	3.8	6.1	5.4	5.2
13	2.7	2.2	3.3	3.2	2.8	8.7	7.1	9.6	9.4	8.7
26	2.9	2.6	4.0	3.8	3.3	9.9	8.8	13.6	12.5	11.2
39	3.2	2.8	4.3	4.5	3.7	11.4	10.0	15.3	16.1	13.2
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	1.8	1.6	1.7	2.1	1.8
<i>Rice</i>										
0	6.6	3.3	5.5	5.2	5.2	13.7	6.8	11.4	11.3	10.8
13	6.7	5.1	6.2	6.6	6.2	17.5	13.3	16.2	17.8	16.2
26	6.7	5.1	6.0	6.6	6.1	17.4	13.2	15.6	18.2	16.1
39	7.0	5.1	6.1	6.6	6.2	18.9	13.8	16.5	18.0	16.8
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.3	2.8	2.9	3.2	4.4	4.1

P removal and changes in available P in soil with extended superphosphate use.

The results are from the PAU farm, where P was applied at graded levels to rice and wheat or to rice or wheat, in which case residual P was measured. Soil was a nonsaline Tulewal loamy sand Ustipsamment with pH 8.4, EC 0.20 mmho/cm, CEC 8.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.23% organic C, and 66-6-108 kg NPK/ha.

P uptake of wheat increased significantly up to 39 kg P/ha and rice

yield and P uptake increased significantly up to 13 kg P/ha (see table). Averaged over 4 yr, rice yielding 5.9 t/ha removed 15.0 kg P/ha; wheat yielding 2.8, 3.3, and 3.7 t/ha removed 8.7, 11.2, and 13.2 kg P/ha. Thus, for an annual 9.9 t/ha of rice and wheat, 29 kg of 52 kg applied P/ha was removed.

Over 4 yr, available soil P increased with successive levels of P application (see figure). The increase was greatest when P was applied to both wheat and rice. Available P increased from 6.8 to

Olsen's P (kg/ha)

Cumulative direct and residual effect of different levels of applied P on Olsen's P in soil (0-15 cm depth) after 4 yr of fertilization.

18.4 kg P/ha when 39 kg P/ha was applied to both crops. P increase was fastest when P was applied to rice. P was more available after rice harvest than after wheat harvest because soil P is more available in submerged than in aerated soils. When P was applied to wheat alone, available P decreased after the next rice crop. *∫*

Control of the azolla pest *Limnea natalensis* with molluscicides of plant origin

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The freshwater snail *L. natalensis* is a serious azolla pest in rice fields and azolla multiplication plots in central Senegal (Saloum Province). Its populations may reach 100 g fresh weight/m² and in 2 wk destroy 500 g azolla inoculum. *Limnea* eat azolla roots, then leaves. They embed eggs on firm translucent sheaths on the lower lobe of the fronds.

L. natalensis also vectors *schistosomiasis*, and control in azolla plots should be considered as a necessary disease prophylactic.

We compared a commercial molluscicide containing metaldehyde with materials obtained from the local

Effect of limnicide treatments on *Limnea natalensis* and *Azolla pinnata* var. *africana*, Dakar, Senegal.^a

Treatment ^b (g/litre)	8 days		15 days	
	<i>Azolla</i> ^c (%)	<i>Limnea</i> ^d (%)	<i>Azolla</i> (%)	<i>Limnea</i> (%)
<i>L. natalensis</i>	79 a	130 a	21 a	100 a
+ metaldehyde	80 a	60 b	45 ab	30 b
0.025	75 a	43 b	60 b	10 bc
0.25	85 a	72 b	110 c	105 a
1.5	76 a	96 c	61 b	90 a
+ neem cake				
+ <i>B. aegyptiaca</i>				
nut powder	73 a	95 c	60 b	0 c
leaf powder	87 a	86 bc	71 b	0 c
0.25	94 a	95 bc	72 b	0 c
0.75	57 b	56 b	0 d	10 bc
1.5	32 b	31 d	0 d	15 bc
3.0				
+ <i>D. heudelotianum</i>				
bark powder	80 a	0 c	81 bc	0 c
0.25				

^a Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.10. ^b Concentrations of plant material are expressed on d.w. basis. ^c f.w. expressed as % of the control with out *L. natalensis*. ^d f.w. of living animals expressed as % of inoculum (2 g).

trees *Azadirachta indica*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, and *Detarium heudelotianum*.

Azolla inoculum corresponding to 500 g fresh weight/m², 2 g fresh weight *L. natalensis*, and the test molluscicide

were placed in plastic containers with 1 litre of medium for azolla. Each treatment had 4 replications. Results were recorded 8 and 15 d after inoculation (see table).

Metaldehyde and neem cake at 1.5

g/litre did not control *L. natalensis*. Metaldehyde inefficiency at the highest concentration and efficiency at lower concentrations may have been due to a protective mechanism developed by

Limnea. B. aegyptiaca nut and leaf powder controlled *L. natalensis*, but concentrations higher than 0.75 g leaf powder/litre harmed azolla. *D. heudelotianum* affected neither

Limnea nor azolla. Treating azolla multiplication plots with 0.25 g *D. heudelotianum* bark powder or *B. aegyptiaca* leaf powder provides an effective, inexpensive control. \mathcal{L}

Nitrogen use efficiency in rice

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We evaluated urea split, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), urea supergranules (USG), and urea coal acid (UCA) with 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for rice at Varanasi. The experiment was in a split-plot design with N sources in main plots and levels in subplots.

Four doses of the coated fertilizers and USG were applied 1 wk after transplanting Jaya. Half of urea split was basal and half in equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. PK at 22-42 kg/ha were applied at transplanting. Fields were flooded with 5±2 cm water throughout the study.

USG performed best, followed by SCU and NCU (see table). Each N increment significantly increased grain yield. \mathcal{L}

Effect of N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983
N sources		
Urea split	3.1	3.0
SCU	3.5	3.2
NCU	3.2	3.2
LCU	2.8	3.1
GCU	3.2	3.0
USG	3.5	3.2
UCA	2.5	3.0
S. Em ±	0.1	0.08
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2
N levels (kg/ha)		
0	2.2	1.9
40	3.0	2.8
80	3.4	3.6
120	3.9	4.1
S. Em ±	0.1	0.06
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2

Effect of sowing time on yield of rice varieties in two locations in Cuba

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Even slight changes in sowing time will substantially change yield and duration of rice varieties. In 1977-80 we recorded the effect of year-around sowing on modern rices.

Varietal response and interaction between variety and sowing date was highly significant in all 36 sowings. Dry season (Nov-Mar) grain yield averaged

1.5 t/ha more than that in wet season (Apr-Oct), independent of variety.

Medium-duration IR880-C9, Caribe-1, and IR1529 performed best when planted from December to August (see figure), depending upon location. Short-duration P723 yielded better when planted from late December to March, and from April to early August. Photoperiod-sensitive Caribe-7 should be planted from April to June.

Because of low temperature during reproductive stage, September to November sowings generally yielded lowest. \mathcal{L}

Favorable sowing range for 5 rices in Cuba.

Seasonal variation in azolla biomass production in Jorhat

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Azolla pinnata grows naturally in low-lying fields, shallow ditches, and channels in Assam. In 1981-82 we

studied azolla biomass production with different levels of inoculants and nutrients (see table) in 4-m² dugout plots lined with 750 gauge black polythene. The experiment had three replications.

Seasonal azolla growth varied significantly. Azolla biomass production increased from Mar to Jun, declined in